
Promoting positive behaviour and mental health in children through Relaxation and Values Education

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Abstract Relaxation practices foster emotional balance and mental composure, serving as practical tools for stress management. It is a simple stress-relief tool. (Patel, 2018). Children become more receptive when they are in a relaxed state. The present paper confines itself to the promotion of mental health through Relaxation and Values Education useful in bringing about positive behaviour in children. A series of interviews conducted for a sample group of students of classes IV & V indicated that Relaxation practice helped them absorb the values better. They became calm from within bringing out positive behaviour traits. Insights from this empirical work conducted by Ravi (2019), highlighted that the integration of Heartfulness Relaxation into Values Education helps establish a classroom atmosphere that is more open and supportive of learning.

This study explored the role of Values Education in shaping the behaviour of students and examined innovative approaches that enhance its effectiveness in school curricula. Values Education is increasingly being recognized as an essential subject in fostering ethical, moral, mental and social development among children. However, its abstract nature makes conventional assessment challenging, calling for alternative methods of evaluation and implementation. Findings from the study indicated that students were able to internalize values more effectively when the subject was combined with relaxation practices, thereby leading to observable positive behavioural changes. Positive behaviour traits reflect sound mental health. This paper therefore underscores the need to reimagine Values Education not only as a curricular subject but also as a transformative methodology that shapes character, fosters empathy and mental health, and nurtures holistic development in students. Strengthening Values Education with heart-based techniques contributes to the cultivation of a value-driven school culture that prepares students to coexist peacefully and contribute positively to society.

Keywords: Relaxation, Behaviour traits, Values Education, Mental health, Holistic Development

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (2018), Mental health is a state of well-being in which every individual realizes his or her own potential, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to her or his community.' A nurturing family environment significantly shapes the values a child absorbs, with stable relationships serving as the foundation for moral growth. Values are essential for positive human behaviour. Schools contribute in their own way towards promoting values in children through Values Education programmes known by different names in different

schools like Moral Science, Life Skills, Personality Development, etc. Heartfulness guided relaxation is offered to children up to the age of fifteen. They become calmer and more relaxed. When Heartfulness Relaxation is offered to the students as part and parcel of their Values Education curriculum, it is observed that they work cooperatively, develop empathy and help others. Values thus imbibed last longer, get expressed in their behaviour and help promote mental health.

Objectives

1. To discuss mental health in terms of positive behaviour in children.
2. To emphasise the role of Heartfulness Relaxation and Values Education in promoting mental health

2. Methodology

Heartfulness is a simple and practical way to experience the heart's unlimited resources. Heartfulness Relaxation is offered to students and also to everyone who want to relax themselves. This paper adopts a Qualitative Exploratory Design with Descriptive analysis to examine the influence of Heartfulness Relaxation and Values Education on Mental Health.

3. Discussion - Mental Health

Schools are not only responsible for teaching academics but also for promoting the mental health of students. Good mental health can be recognized not only by the absence of disorders but also by the presence of self-acceptance, resilience, self-esteem and positive coping skills. These skills contribute to good behaviour in students. While families provide the primary support for developing children's mental health, institutions like schools also support by playing an important role working with students and families. Most students' needs will be adequately met in a positive and engaging school environment.

Relationship between positive behaviour and mental health

People who are happier and more satisfied and complacent in life are much more likely to be kind, tolerant and inclusive. So, that's the direct way in which society benefits when children grow up with such attributes.

Children who are mentally healthy have the ability to:

- develop psychologically, emotionally, intellectually and spiritually
- initiate, develop and sustain mutually satisfying personal relationships
- use and enjoy solitude
- become aware of others and empathise with them
- play and learn
- develop a sense of right and wrong
- resolve (face) problems and setbacks and learn from them

Positive behaviour traits such as above can be fostered in schools through an effective Values Education programme. According to Dr. Clete Bulach (Bulach, 2000), any Values Education program that helps in improved behaviour related to the following 16 character traits should be considered effective and implemented in schools:

- respect for self, others and property
- honesty
- self-control/discipline
- responsibility/dependability/accountability
- cooperation
- integrity/fairness
- kindness
- perseverance/diligence/motivation
- compassion/empathy
- courtesy/politeness
- forgiveness
- patriotism/citizenship
- tolerance of diversity
- humility

- generosity/charity
- sportsmanship

Research studies on promoting mental health of children

A number of practices have been shown to improve the mental health.

Mindfulness: Mindfulness rooted in Buddhist meditation, involves consciously attending to one's thoughts, emotions and sensations in the present without judgement.

Felicia Huppert, director of the Well Being Institute at the University of Cambridge and Professor of Psychology at the Institute for Positive Psychology and Education at the Australian Catholic University, studied mental wellbeing and Mindfulness for more than two decades. Huppert (2009) emphasized that Mindfulness enhances emotional awareness, thereby improving behavioural regulation and relationships. For instance, if we are aware that we are becoming angry, we have a greater ability to make a choice of how to behave in response to that emotion with the practice of Mindfulness. Research studies also show that Mindfulness is effective at improving mental well-being, behaviour regulation and interpersonal relationships.

Some of the ways in which schools can promote their pupils' mental health include:

- a) Clear policies on behaviour, bullying and the range of acceptable and unacceptable behaviour for children that set out the responsibilities of everyone in the school.
- b) Making use of an effective Values Education curriculum throughout the whole school to promote mental health and well-being.
- c) Teachers are supported to deliver practical sessions about mental health issues, the importance of sleep and practical relaxation techniques such as Yoga.

Recently, there has also been growth of interest in 'brain compatible' learning which draws on research in the neurosciences. Brighter Minds is an educational initiative to equip every child with tools and methods to enhance cognitive functioning for achieving personal excellence and instil confidence in oneself. This program provides a learning environment based on joy, positivity, and love. It is beneficial in increasing the emotional stability and balance.

Heartfulness Relaxation and Values Education

Ravi (2019) conducted an empirical study to examine the effect of Values Education on student behaviour and the role of Heartfulness Relaxation in enhancing its impact. The study revealed that students responded more positively when Values Education was taught in combination with relaxation practices, as this created a supportive environment for absorbing values effectively. A sample group of students from classes IV and V was selected through random sampling from three different schools. All the three schools offered Heartfulness Relaxation and meditation to their students. Each of the schools has a specified syllabus for Values Education as part of their school curriculum. Facilitators begin the Values Education lesson by asking the students to close their eyes and go into the quiet place in their hearts (preferably sitting in a circle somewhere quiet). Before starting this, first the facilitator is trained to centre herself/himself in the heart, holding the quiet time for up to 2 minutes.

During the course of the academic year, the students were interviewed and data was collected to assess the effect of Heartfulness Relaxation and Values Education in bringing about peace and calmness and changes in their behaviour. As discussed earlier, an improvement in the above indicate sound mental health.

Children appreciated the inclusion of Values Education in their school curriculum and elaborated the benefits. According to the primary data collected, Heartfulness Relaxation, meditation and Values Education help them:

- To be at peace, happy and calm.
- To learn about what is around, to maintain discipline.
- To get basic idea on spiritual values.
- To care about living, help others, love and care about others.
- To learn value based behaviour and being good citizens when they grow up.
- To practice values like truth and wisdom, apologizing, love and compassion, and spirituality.
- To make them good students, learning good things, behaving in class, sharing and learning communication.
- To learn about environment, learn to do things like donations to the poor, waste disposal, etc.
- To learn self - control, self-awareness, friendliness, respect, obedience and kindness.

- To understand values like ‘health is wealth’, acceptance of mistakes, being bold, courageous, brave and focus.
- To learn about useful things for life like keeping surroundings clean, good habits and morals from stories, safety rules, animal care and family.
- To be participative, avoid fighting and blaming others.
- To learn manners and behaviour, mind control, being pleasant and polite.
- Self – management through Heartfulness Relaxation and Meditation techniques to overcome irritation and be better, following all the values we should have in ourselves.

4. Conclusion

A substantial body of research demonstrates that relaxation practices are beneficial in managing stress, anxiety and pain. Heartfulness Relaxation helps children relax each and every part of their body from toe to head and then centre themselves in their hearts. When values are taught in such a state of mind, children are able to absorb them through their hearts and follow them naturally throughout their lives. The study also highlighted that gender influenced students’ perceptions, with girls showing higher value-related behavioural outcomes than boys, and that Grade IV students reported stronger perceptions compared to Grade V students. This suggests that Values Education should be experiential and age-appropriate. A survey was conducted to collect information from teachers of various schools. All of them expressed their concern on the current status of Values Education and stressed the importance of implementing Values Education programs in all schools with more rigour.

Values Education plays a significant role in the holistic development of students. In this context, schools are encouraged to integrate the Heartfulness Relaxation technique alongside Values Education curricula, as such practices not only support students’ emotional well-being, balanced state of mind and sound mental health but also contribute to the broader good of society.

Despite its mandatory status, Values Education in India lacks a uniform National syllabus, leaving schools with the responsibility of adapting and updating their programs to ensure that content remains engaging, developmentally appropriate, and inclusive for both boys and girls across all grade levels.

To enhance the effectiveness of implementation, the use of structured textbooks accompanied by well-designed lesson plans for teachers can facilitate the smooth delivery of Values Education. Responding to this need, the Heartfulness Institute, through its educational wing, the Heartfulness Education Trust, has developed The Heartfulness Way Curriculum. This program equips students with tools for experiential, activity-based learning that fosters self-discovery, balance, and overall well-being. The curriculum was developed by an international team comprising school teachers, university lecturers, occupational therapists, counsellors, PhD scholars in education, and experienced facilitators from India, Europe, North America, Australia, and New Zealand. It is grounded in the framework of “Core Human Values” as outlined in UNESCO’s Learning to Be: A Holistic and Integrated Approach to Values Education for Human Development (APNIEVE & UNESCO, 2002). Each grade level is supported by two books—one providing lesson plans for teachers and another offering activity-based exercises for students.

Furthermore, an explicit and time-tabled Values Education program, delivered by teachers specifically trained in this area, is more likely to achieve meaningful outcomes. Regular modifications and updates to the curriculum are also essential for maintaining relevance. To this end, the Heartfulness Education Trust proposes the Heartfulness Education and Resources for Teachers (HEART) program, a year-long professional development initiative. This training equips educators with Heartfulness practices, life skills, and pedagogical knowledge, thereby enabling them to deliver Values Education more effectively and to foster quality educational outcomes by promoting positive behaviour and mental health in children.

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